

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

BY USING THE LAWS OF PHYSICS, IT IS POSSIBLE TO BRING BACK TO LIFE A PERSON WHO HAS DIED, FOR EXAMPLE, AS A RESULT OF AN ACCIDENT OR CRIME¹

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Abstract

In the article it is suggested that due to the fast (faster than the Earth rotates) movement on the Earth through time zones to carry out accessible to people travelling (for example, by plane) both in the past and in the future time. An example of realisation of such time travel routes is given, allowing to bring back to life people who died as a result of an accident or criminal humans activity.

Keywords: arrow of time, corrected version of the special theory of relativity, anti-time, internal time, external time, time zones, time travels.

1. Introduction

The title of the article may be perplexing. What can physics have to do with bringing a person back to life? Especially not in science fiction, but in serious science? But, it turns out, it can, although this serious science itself does not agree with this opinion.

The fact is that it is possible to bring a person back to life by travelling through time. But the possibility of travelling in time, except for some purely theoretical situations - in the twin paradox of the special theory of relativity (SRT), as a result of teleportations in quantum mechanics and in some other exotic theoretical situations - in practical human activity is denied by physics even in the distant future.

However, this article provides descriptions of useful new human activities that are physically already feasible on Earth now using time travel to the past and into the future.

2. Proof of the physical reality of time travel on Earth is already in the present day

Here are a couple of quotes that illustrate the current state of understanding of the problem of time. *"Time is the most frequently used word in the English language and the third most frequently used word in Russian. It is also frequently used in all other languages, too, because synchronizing actions in time is as important as coordinating them in space. Without knowing the exact time, it is impossible to organize your life and plan it in advance. If in ancient times you could rely on natural cycles and an internal sense of time, then in our days you must constantly have a watch or a phone with you. Time is the most important of the abstract concepts that we pronounce every day. Every thinking person has thought about the problem of time at least once in his life. And a huge amount of philosophical and scientific literature has been written on this topic. Nevertheless, no one can say with certainty even what time is."* [1]

And here is what Stephen William Hawking writes about this [2]: *"In ordinary life, there is a huge difference between moving forward and backward in time. Imagine that a cup of water falls from a table and*

breaks into pieces. If you film this fall, then when you watch the film, it will immediately become clear whether the film is running forward or backward. If it is running backward, then we will see how the fragments lying on the floor suddenly come together and, having formed a whole cup, jump onto the table. And you will be able to claim that the film was running backward, because in ordinary life this does not happen. Otherwise, all the faience factories would have to be closed."

This phenomenon, known as the 'arrow of time', is one of the most surprising problems in physics. The name 'arrow of time' was proposed by the British physicist Sir Arthur Stanley Eddington in the early XX century [3]. And all our life experience, as it would seem, confirms the truth of this concept.

But the corrected version of SRT [4]-[12], in which a new concept of 'anti-time' has appeared, induces this life experience to be corrected. Indeed, if we assume that soon travelling through the expanses of universes and antiverse of the hidden Multiverse will become possible for people on Earth, then time travel [13] will also become possible, both in the past and in the future.

Moreover, time travel on Earth is already not only possible now, but also exists, although it is not used [14]-[25]. And since they are much easier and cheaper than in space, we will consider them. At the same time we will need two new concepts - internal (or biological) time of a human being and external time of his environment. And these two times have different properties. Human biological time cannot flow backwards. That is, a person cannot return to his youth or childhood. But the situation in the external environment in which a human being is, as a result of human activity, can change in the most incredible way. And in this external environment it is already possible to move both to the future and to the past time. And even short-term movements in time can be very useful. For example, if you get an opportunity to look into the future time for a short time,

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security service. However, even Presidents do not recover so quickly. And to explain to the people how the President was brought back to life is to be inexpedient, as it is not known how it will be perceived by them. However, this can be remedied: the President will simply have to stay out of public view for the duration of his alleged treatment. Secondly, the President with the head of the security service and the rest of the citizens have so far found themselves existing on Earth in

different times. And this circumstance is already more difficult to overcome.

And there can be only one way out of this situation – the President and the head of the security service, in order to return to the same time in which the rest of the people of the Earth are, need to make a journey into the future (see Fig. 2).

Fig.2. Time-travelling routes of the President and the head of the security service, ensuring the President's return to life after the assassination attempt, as well as the rest of the Earth's inhabitants. The solid lines represent their movements on the surface of the Earth, and the dotted lines represent the movements of the President and the head of security by aeroplane across time zones.

Therefore let's continue. After the President and the head of the security service have solved all their issues in the past time ("d" in Fig. 2), they get on a plane and fly around Antarctica in the opposite direction ("e" in Fig. 2). And thus in 24 hours they return from the past to the present ("d+e" in Fig. 2). And while they are flying, they have time to discuss their problems of the future. And after the plane arrives in the present, the President, together with the head of the security service, secretly gets into a car and leaves for a place of stay chosen on board the plane for the duration of his alleged treatment. And after the completion of this 'healing' ("f" in Fig. 2), the President already appears in his residence. And since the conditions $a + b = g$ and $d + f = h$ were met in such a time travel (see Fig. 2) then, eventually, the President and the head of the security service returned to the same time in which all the other people of the Earth were.

This is how, presumably, the problem of bringing back to life people who have died as a result of an accident or someone else's criminal activity can be solved. But it is not excluded that during the realisation of the solution to this problem, additional circumstances may arise that will require their own solution. And which, hopefully, will turn out to be solvable.

4. Conclusion

The above are just assumptions that need to be verified experimentally. Moreover, these verification experiments are simple, easy to implement and quite convincing. But you need an airplane. And having flown around the North or South Pole through 24 time zones and having made sure that they actually got to the past or future time, the experimenters will get an answer to their question of whether they can actually travel in

time. And after that, they can return to their present time in the manner described above. And if such an experiment confirms the assumptions made in the article, then the above-described and other travel routes to the past and future can be used to solve other problems. For example, simply by asking a passer-by what the date and time are, or by using your iPhone for this purpose. And the knowledge gained in this way can also be used to create more comfortable time machines.

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